

THE EDUCATIONAL POINTS DESCRIBED IN I AM MALALA

¹Muxtasarxon Azimova Jaloldin qizi,

²Niyozov Sirojiddin Baxtiyorovich

Uzbekistan State World Languages University.

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Annotation: I AM MALALA is the remarkable tale of a family uprooted by global terrorism, of the fight for girls' education, of a father who, himself a school owner, championed and encouraged his daughter to write and attend school, and of brave parents who have a fierce love for their daughter in a society that prizes sons.

Key words: education, story, learn, right, book, women, Taliban, power, school, religious, values

Malala Yousafzai born 12 July 1997, is a Pakistani female education activist and the 2014 Nobel Peace Prize laureate. Awarded when she was 17, she is the world's youngest Nobel Prize laureate, and the second Pakistani and the first Pashtun to receive a Nobel Prize. This book was published on 8 October 2013, by Weidenfeld and Nicolson in the UK and Little, Brown and Company in the US. I Am Malala, an account of the life of main author Malala Yousafzai, has been translated into 40 languages, and has sold close to two million copies worldwide. I Am Malala is a story about a young girl's campaign for human rights, especially a woman's right to education. The power of this story is that it is true. Truth, justice, forgiveness, and equality—these are the universal human values, and they are the lessons instilled in Malala's book.

From the first scene, in which Malala is shot by the Taliban for riding a bus to school to the final chapter in which Malala lobbies for a UN resolution in favor of universal education—I Am Malala celebrates the importance of education. It could be said that education determines the way Malala comes of age: the more she learns, the more she recognizes the value of learning, and the more mature she becomes.

Education empowers people, not only by giving them knowledge that they can use to gain power, but by encouraging them to have confidence in themselves. Ziauddin, Malala's father, knows this first-hand. As a child, he struggles to overcome a stammer and assert himself before his proud, intimidating father, Rohul Amin. Ziauddin studies literature and rhetoric, eventually winning a series of prestigious speaking competitions. In this way, he overcomes his stammer, and develops the drive and work ethic that continue to make him a successful political figure for years afterwards. From an early age, Malala is aware of Ziauddin's self-education. One of the earliest parts of her education, one might

say, is her realization that she can do anything with the proper studying and preparation.

As Malala grows up, her respect for education grows. While she does well on her exams. She usually ranking at the top of her class. Her most important moments of learning come when she sees the impact of education on others. This is particularly clear in the chapter where Malala goes to Islamabad with her father's friend, ShizaShahid. In the large, cosmopolitan city, Malala is overjoyed to see women with professional careers and strong, forceful personalities. Each of these women tells Malala the same thing: pursue your education at all costs. It's no coincidence that when Malala returns to her native town of Mingora, she throws herself into her political projects: condemning the Taliban for their opposition to universal education, making radio broadcasts, and reaching out to struggling women around her country. Malala's coming-of-age largely consists of her increasing recognition of the value of learning.

There's never a moment in *I Am Malala* where Malala has serious doubts about the value of education—indeed, the only change in her attitude toward education is that she comes to value it more and more. As the book ends, Malala is stronger and more mature than ever, and thus, more confident about the value of education. In the final chapter, she embarks on her most ambitious project yet: a United Nations resolution designed to ensure an education for every child on the planet. Malala Yousafzai is a girls' education activist and the co-founder and board chair of Malala Fund. In 2014, she received the Nobel peace prize in recognition of her efforts to see every girl complete 12 years of free, safe, quality education.

Novel *I Am Malala* tells of a girl from the Swat Valley who lives within the Taliban militant regime that prohibits girls going to school. Some way that the Taliban do to prohibit women to go to school is by bombing schools for girls and boys, and threatened to kill anyone who opposes the ban of Taliban. But it does not dampen the Malala's spirit to go to school. This novel not only tells the community around Malala, but also the story of her struggle can inspire others. *I Am Malala* novel received public attention because of Malala's courage to resist the Taliban in a democratic way. The novel tells about a struggle of a girl to get her education, she expressed her protest through press conferences and persuaded many people in Pakistan to care about education, it is not only for boys but also for girls. Because of her courage, Malala gets threat from the Taliban and she almost killed by the Taliban's bullets that deliberately fired to Malala in October 2012. Malala shootings become the public talks in the various

countries and it scared Taliban and asked her to return to the Pakistan after being treated in the UK.

This novel inspired many people about the important of education that should not be wasted. I Am Malala became a novel that suggested by world leaders to read, because it contained educational values that useful for people.

Educational value is a value created and accepted by everyone without disregarding the function of education. The value of education is a value that can make people as a religious, social and moral person. The values should be appreciated and understood by human beings because the educational value leads the goodness in thinking or acting, so it can develop one's mind and character.

The educational values in novel I Am Malala has inspired the world wide about how the importance of education must be owned by everyone.

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